

ANALYSIS OF MECHANICAL FILTERING PROPERTIES OF PERIODIC LAMINATES

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ABSTRACT

Periodic structures elements possess filtering properties that prevent wave propagation in some frequency ranges, usually designated as stopbands. These properties have had reduced use in mechanical design, namely in laminated structures, notwithstanding the fact some applications have been reported e.g. for cylindrical shells stiffened with rings. Seeking qualitative insight for design suggestions is one of the major objectives of the communication.

Both the cases of isotropic and of orthotropic component lamina are examined. A brief review of techniques based on the so-called Floquet theory is presented. The study evidences that the response depends on only two parameters for isotropy - the ratio of impedances, as well as the ratio of the times required for the waves to travel across the media - that contain the information necessary to establish the width of the stop and passbands and, together with the ratios of orthotropy, are the control variables to consider.

KEYWORDS: Composites; Laminates; Orthotropy; Stopbands.

1. INTRODUCTION

Composite materials have been developing for decades, with great stimulus derived from applications of laminates. In this note, the focus is placed on the wave propagation characteristics of some laminates, considered periodic and elastic. The technical interest of the study of wave propagation in stratified solid media has increased due to the mechanical filtering properties which can be explored in acoustic isolation, on improvement of structural behavior and on the attenuation of dynamic excitation in frequency regions of large spectral amplification. The equations encountered are of Hill type and a classic book for such

equations is due to Mc Lachlan [1]. The extension from one-dimensional domains to higher dimensions i.e. from ordinary differential equations (ODE) to partial differential equations (PDE), as proposed by Bloch, can be found in [2]. A great variety of physical problems lead to equivalent mathematical models. R.L. Kronig and W.G. Penney [3] reported the results of the analysis of a problem formulated via a Bloch wave equation in the case of an intermittent rectangular potential $V(x)$, of period $(a+b)$, often called square well potential. The governing equation is

$$\frac{d^2 y}{dx^2} + K^2 [W - V(x)] y = 0 \quad (1)$$

with

$$V(x) = \begin{cases} 0 & \text{for } 0 < x \leq a \\ V_0 & \text{for } a < x < (a + b) \end{cases} \quad (2)$$

The solution is given in the form $y(x) = u(x) e^{i\alpha x}$ where the quasi-periodic unknown $y(x)$ is replaced by the unknown periodic function $u(x) = u(x+a+b)$ and by the wave number α and this formulation typifies most procedures used to solve this class of problems. T. Thomson, as early as 1950, studied the transmission of plane elastic waves through a layered medium [4]. E. H. Lee, working basically on a one-dimension composite, surveyed variational methods applicable to elastic wave propagation [5]. The survey contains also an analysis of propagation of harmonic waves on these periodic systems. L. R. Lewis and A. Hessel, addressed the problem of propagation on periodic arrays of dielectric slabs [6]. Similar systems occur in geomechanics, a reference being made here to [7]. M. Ohlrich studied low frequency vibration and noise problems in lightweight multi-storeyed buildings [8], while G. Herrmann has done extensive work on similar applications in mechanics [9] and together with A. M. Braga has been applying techniques successful in other fields of mathematical physics to the elastodynamics of composites [10]. M. Schoenberg, among others, addressed problems involving interaction of fluid and solids. Helbig extended the studies to anisotropy [11]. Finally, extensive research has been developed by D. J. Mead and his co-workers that is relevant for structural analysis [12].

2. EQUATION OF MOTION AND BOUNDARY CONDITIONS

Physical periodicity is considered, hereafter, to mean periodically varying material properties and coherently periodic boundary conditions. Wave propagation in such periodic systems is characterized by the presence of frequency bands for which there is free propagation, separated by alternating bands of attenuation.

In the sequel, the propagation problem for perfectly bonded, parallel, spatially periodic lamellae, with the plane of layering being of material symmetry, is examined. The treatment of periodic boundary conditions is ensured by requiring that, at all times, the interface traction and displacement have the same value, respectively, at both surfaces limiting the

"cell" whose repetition generates the spatial periodicity. The one-dimensional case of a laminate formed of parallel, homogeneous layers, in the absence of body forces, is mathematically modeled by

$$\left[\frac{\partial}{\partial x} \left(R(x) \frac{\partial}{\partial x} \right) - \rho(x) \frac{\partial^2}{\partial t^2} \right] U(x,t) = 0 \tag{3}$$

where $R(x)$ introduces the stiffness, $\rho(x)$ is the mass density and $U(x,t)$ the displacement field. It is assumed that $R(x)$ and $\rho(x)$ obey $R(x+d)=R(x)$, $\rho(x+d)=\rho(x)$. For harmonic motions of circular frequency ω and isotropic material, the elimination of time leads to an ODE in x . A straight application of Floquet theorem is, then, feasible since $B(x)$ and $\rho(x)$ are periodic functions, and $F(x)$ is sought with the same period d via:

$$u(x) = F(x) e^{ik_x x} \tag{4}$$

Parameter k_x is known as Floquet wave number and (4) may formulate (i) the longitudinal motion in an elastic rod, when $B(x) = \lambda(x) + 2\mu(x)$ and λ and μ are Lamé constants, or (ii) transverse anti-plane elastic waves when $U(x,t)$ is the displacement normal to the direction of propagation and $B(x)$ is the shear modulus of a 3-D medium. Recently, efforts to learn how to select geometric and elastic characteristics of each layer in a way that allows the control of the width and spectral location of the stopping and passing bands have been reported[13]. The geometry of the systems under analysis is depicted in Fig. 1.

Figure 1. Periodic, unbounded, laminated medium

The equations of motion for an anisotropic elastic solid are

$$c_{ijkl} \frac{\partial^2 u_k}{\partial x_i \partial x_j} + \rho f_i = \rho \frac{\partial^2 u_i}{\partial t^2} \tag{5}$$

where c_{ijkl} is the strain tensor, f_i represents volume forces and the stiffnesses c_{ijkl} relate stresses and strains via $\sigma_{ij} = c_{ijkl} e_{kl}$. In the case of orthotropy there are nine

independent constants ($c_{11}, c_{12}, c_{13}, c_{22}, c_{23}, c_{33}, c_{44}, c_{55}, c_{66}$). The axes of reference are assumed to coincide with the material axes for the selected notation to hold. Seeking solutions for (5) of the type

$$u_k = U_k e^{i\left(\frac{2\pi}{\lambda}\right)(n_j x_j - vt)} \quad (6)$$

where components n_j define the unit vector normal to the wave front, v measures the phase velocity and U_i characterize the amplitude of the displacement of the particles, non-trivial U_i require that the dispersion equation holds:

$$\begin{vmatrix} h_{11} - \rho v^2 & h_{12} & h_{13} \\ h_{12} & h_{22} - \rho v^2 & h_{23} \\ h_{13} & h_{23} & h_{33} - \rho v^2 \end{vmatrix} = 0 \quad (7)$$

where

$$h_{ik} = n_j n_l c_{ijkl}, \quad h_{ik} = h_{ki} \quad (8)$$

For each selected ray vector \vec{n} , (7) supplies three values of the velocity v and, for each one of the latter, the corresponding amplitude displacement vector (U_1, U_2, U_3). The elimination of the components of the stress tensor into the equations of motion leads to the Navier displacement equations that, for anti-plane, transverse shear motion reduce to:

$$\mu_{xy} \frac{\partial^2 u}{\partial y^2} + \mu_{xz} \frac{\partial^2 u}{\partial z^2} = \rho \frac{\partial^2 u}{\partial t^2} \quad (9)$$

For each layer, the solution can be sought as

$$u = C f(z) e^{i(k_y y - \omega t)} \quad (10)$$

where ω is the circular frequency of the time harmonic traveling wave and k_y is the wave number in the y -direction. The resulting ordinary differential equation is:

$$f''(z) + \frac{\rho\omega^2 - k_y^2 \mu_{xy}}{\mu_{xz}} f(z) = 0 \quad (11)$$

The three-dimensional theory of Bloch applied to the layered medium introduces a z exponential transfer across the cells that imposes a decay of amplitude and no propagation for non-real k_z :

$$u(y, z, t) = u(y, z + d, t) e^{-ik_z d} \quad (12)$$

where $d = 2(h_m + h_f)$ is the total thickness of the cell.

The continuity of traction and displacement at the interface requires, at each cell:

$$\sigma_{xz}^{(f)}(y_N, h_f, t) = \sigma_{xz}^{(m)}(y_{N+1}, -h_m, t) \quad (13.a)$$

$$u^{(f)}(y_N, h_f, t) = u^{(m)}(y_{N+1}, -h_m, t) \quad (13.b)$$

$$\sigma_{xz}^{(f)}(y_{N+1}, -h_f, t) = \sigma_{xz}^{(m)}(y_N, h_m, t) \quad (13.c)$$

$$u^{(f)}(y_{N+1}, -h_f, t) = u^{(m)}(y_N, h_m, t) \quad (13.d)$$

where (N) and (N+1) designate generic consecutive cells (Fig. 1). The expressions refer to a homogeneous orthotropic layer and are valid for its material axes. The analysis of "stacked" layers to form the composite laminates requires that all relevant quantities be expressed in the same global coordinate system. Let local $Ox_1x_2x_3$ differ from $Ox'_1x'_2x'_3$ by a counterclockwise rotation θ about Ox_3 and primes (or their absence) identify the frame on which the quantities are expressed. Consider $\sigma'_{kl} = a_{ki} a_{lj} \sigma_{ij}$ where a_{ij} are the direction co-sines and:

$$A = |a_{ij}| = \begin{vmatrix} \cos^2\theta & \sin^2\theta & 0 & 0 & 0 & 2\sin\theta\cos\theta \\ \sin^2\theta & \cos^2\theta & 0 & 0 & 0 & -2\sin\theta\cos\theta \\ 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & \cos\theta & -\sin\theta & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & \sin\theta & \cos\theta & 0 \\ -\sin\theta\cos\theta & \sin\theta\cos\theta & 0 & 0 & 0 & \cos^2\theta - \sin^2\theta \end{vmatrix} \quad (14)$$

For each layer in anti-plane shear, the stress components relevant at the interface are given by: $\sigma_{xz} = c_{55}(\partial u/\partial z) + c_{56}(\partial u/\partial y) = c_{55}(\partial u/\partial z)$, $\sigma_{yz} = c_{45}(\partial u/\partial z) + c_{46}(\partial u/\partial y) = 0$.

For later use, $\sigma'_{23} = -c_{55}(\partial u/\partial z)\sin\theta$ and $\sigma'_{13} = c_{55}(\partial u/\partial z)\cos\theta$.

In the examples, θ will be taken as $\theta=0$, corresponding to alignment of material and global axes. For cross ply laminates, the stiffnesses shall be interpreted, e.g., as if for one layer $Ox_1 \equiv Ox'_1$ and in the next layer $Ox_2 \equiv Ox'_1$. The orthotropic stress-strain relations, in material coordinates, show that $\sigma_{yz} \equiv 0$ and $\sigma_{xz} = c_{55}(\partial u/\partial z)$.

3. DISPERSION

The general expression for anti-plane transverse waves associated with (9) is:

$$u = e^{i(\pi/2h)[(Y'/r)y - \sqrt{\mu_{xy}/\rho} \Omega' t]} \cdot [A e^{i(\pi/2h)\alpha'z} + B e^{-i(\pi/2h)\alpha'z}] \quad (15)$$

with

$$\Omega' = (2h/\pi) \omega / \sqrt{\mu_{xz}/\rho}, \quad Y' = (2h/\pi) k_y (\mu_{xy}/\mu_{xz}) \quad (16.a)$$

that define

$$c_{xz} = \sqrt{\mu_{xz}/\rho}, \quad \alpha' = \sqrt{\Omega'^2 - Y'^2} \quad (16.b)$$

where the length h was introduced for adimensionalization. The ratio of the shear moduli introduces the orthotropy and is defined by the parameter r :

$$r = \frac{\mu_{xy}}{\mu_{xz}} \quad (17)$$

The equation of dispersion, after algebraic manipulations, becomes

$$4\bar{r} b_o \cos \left[\pi (1 + \bar{r} \bar{h}) k_\zeta \right] + \left[(1 - \bar{r} b_o \bar{\delta})^2 / \bar{\delta} \right] \cdot \cos \left[\pi \sqrt{\bar{r}_f} \alpha (1 - a_o \bar{\delta}) \right] - \left[(1 + \bar{r} b_o \bar{\delta})^2 / \bar{\delta} \right] \cos \left[\pi \sqrt{\bar{r}_f} \alpha (1 + a_o \bar{\delta}) \right] = 0 \quad (18)$$

with

$$b_o = (\rho_m c_m) / (\rho_f c_f), \quad a_o = (h_f/c_f) / (h_m/c_m) \quad (19.a)$$

$$\bar{h} = h_m/h_f, \quad \bar{r} = (r_m/r_f)^{1/2} \quad (19.b)$$

$$k_\zeta = (2\sqrt{\bar{r}_f} h_f/\pi) k_z, \quad k_\eta = (2\sqrt{\bar{r}_f} h_f/\pi) k_y \quad (19.c)$$

$$\sigma = (c_f/c_m), \quad \bar{\delta} = \left[(\Omega^2 - (\bar{r} Y/\sigma)^2) / (\Omega^2 - Y^2) \right]^{1/2} \quad (19.d)$$

and defines a surface of dispersion on $\Omega k_\eta k_\zeta$. The surface has planes of discontinuity for $k_\zeta(1 + \bar{r} \bar{h}) = n$, $n = 1, 2, \dots$. Complex branches correspond to non-real k_ζ and are associated with stopping bands i.e. frequency regions where harmonic waves are attenuated as seen from (15).

Symmetric and anti-symmetric modes (opposite symmetry) intersect at conical points where the frequencies coalesce and the width of the stopping band vanishes [9], a result that is typical of Hill equations. The width of passbands never vanishes. For the simpler case of isotropic lamina, the equation of dispersion can be written:

$$4b_o \cos(k_z d) + \frac{(1 - b_o \bar{\delta})^2}{\bar{\delta}} \cos[\pi \alpha (1 - a_o \bar{\delta})] - \frac{(1 + b_o \bar{\delta})^2}{\bar{\delta}} \cos[\pi \alpha (1 + a_o \bar{\delta})] = 0 \quad (20)$$

with $\delta = (\bar{\alpha}/\alpha)$, $\bar{\alpha} = \sqrt{\Omega^2 - (Y/\sigma)^2}$, $\Omega = \left(\frac{2h_f}{\pi} \right) \frac{\omega}{c_f}$

This formulation evidences that the roots for the edge bands ($k_z d = 0, \pi$) for propagation normal to layering depend exclusively on a_0 and b_0 , an important fact usually undetected due to the obscure expressions used for the equation of dispersion.

4. RESULTS

The results obtained numerically for waves propagating normally to the layers show (i) ways to control the attenuation characteristics of laminates designed to filter selected frequency regions and (ii) add insight to some properties of the systems.

Fig. 2 shows the variation of the first stopping band with a_0 ($a_0 = 0.5, 1.0, 2.0$) while b_0 varies to in the interval $[0.25, 4.0]$ for isotropic systems. It is noticed that $b_0 = 1$, i.e. equal impedance of the two materials, a condition known to ensure no reflectivity at the interface, is associated with the coalescence of two roots of the characteristic equation and the intersection of the locii of the two lowest roots of (16).

Figure 2. Width of first band for different values of a_0

Data based on Chevalier [14], for a laminate made of steel and plexiglas, was used for eventual comparison. Thicknesses are 2 mm and 3 mm, shear moduli 86.7 MPa and 2.0 MPa (approx.) and $\rho = 7800, 1185 \text{ Kg/m}^3$. The first attenuation band is limited, in Hz, by $f_1 = 0.5 \Omega_1 / (2h_f/t_f) = 0.5 \Omega_1 / t_f = 2.63 \text{ KHz}$, and $f_2 = 2.75 \text{ KHz}$ and the second by $f_3 = 5.23 \text{ KHz}$ and $f_4 = 5.48 \text{ KHz}$. Fig. 3 shows how the width of each of the two bands can change, keeping the materials i.e. $b_0 = 1.17$, while varying $a_0 = (h_f/h_m)(c_m/c_f)$ i.e. the thickness ratio (h_f/h_m).

Figure 3. First two bands for steel'plexiglas example

Additionally, Fig. 4 depicts the three first attenuation bands for $a_0 = 0.75$.

$Azero = 0.75$

Figure 4. Three first stopping bands for $a_0 = 0.75$. Variation with b_0

Data generated for orthotropy is summarized in Figs. 5 and 6. Fig. 5 shows the results that define the edges of the bands for $r_f = 0.25$, $r_m/r_f = 0.50$ and $a_0 = 0.75$. The trends known from isotropy are repeated, but the coalescence of the roots appears, now, for higher b_0 . In fact, for propagation normal to the plane, from (18), $B_0 = \bar{r} b_0 = 1$ leads to the intersection of the edgebands occurs for $b_0 = \sqrt{2}$ in the selected example.

Fig. 6 illustrates the effect of changes on the orthotropy ratio r , assumed equal for both layers, for a value of a_0 equal to that of the steel-plexiglas used for isotropy. Larger values of anisotropy cause the appearance of a larger number of bands, in the same range of Ω . Conversely, the width of the first stopband decreases for increasing $r_f = \mu_{xy}^{(f)} / \mu_{xy}^{(f)}$.

Figure 5. Two lowest stopbands for orthotropic system
 ($a_0 = 0.75$, $\bar{r} = \sqrt{0.5}$, $r_f = 0.55$)

Figure 6. Influence of $r = \mu_{xy} / \mu_{xz}$ on the attenuation bands
 for $(r_f/r_m) = 1$ and $a_0 = (h_f/h_m) (c_m/c_f) = 0.2$

The sensitivity of the bands to the different parameters will be reported in greater detail elsewhere. In quantitative terms, for $\bar{r} = 1$, $r_f = 4$, the effects e.g. of a change of the thickness ratio on the width of the first band are shown below.

b_0	$a_0 = 0.75$		$a_0 = 1.00$	
	Ω_1	Ω_2	Ω_1	Ω_2
1.00	0.2787	0.2927	0.2437	0.2563
1.50	0.2475	0.3225	0.2175	0.2775
2.00	0.2175	0.3552	0.2025	0.3000
2.50	0.2025	0.3675	0.1725	0.3225

5. CONCLUDING REMARKS

The study reports early results on the effects of orthotropy on the attenuation bands of periodic laminates supporting transverse, anti-plane shear waves propagating normally to the plane of layering. The width of the bands, as well as the location of the points of no reflectivity, were shown to be dependent on two parameters in addition to those found for isotropy: the orthotropy ratio $r = \mu_{xy} / \mu_{xz}$, for one of the materials, and the relative ratio (r_f / r_m) . A systematic search of geometric and mechanical characteristics of the laminates to control the location and size of the attenuation bands is now, possible and being undertaken. Changes due to obliquity of wave propagation as well as the establishment of the limits beyond which the infinite media approach has to be replaced by studies that account for the finiteness of the systems are topics to be explored in the future, as well as the extension to plane strain problems.

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